

PREOPERATIVE ANXIETY AND ASSOCIATED FACTORS AMONG WOMEN UNDERGOING CESAREAN SECTION

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Abstract

Background: Anxiety is prevalent among patients undergoing surgical procedures, such as cesarean sections. Perioperative anxiety may have a negative effect on physiological indices and postoperative recovery. The objective of this study was to determine the prevalence and risk factors of perioperative anxiety among patients undergoing cesarean sections.

Objectives: The objectives of this study are to determine the factors that affect preoperative anxiety in women who undergo cesarean deliveries.

Methodology: This cross-sectional study included 145 women who were scheduled for elective cesarean section. Data on their medical history, obstetric history, and sociodemographic information were collected using a questionnaire.

Results: Preoperative anxiety among patients undergoing cesarean section has several contributing factors. Mild anxiety was the most prevalent and was due to waiting before surgery, fear of medical errors, and fear of unexpected outcomes. Moderate anxiety was due to fear of postoperative pain, blood transfusion, and surgical complications. Severe anxiety was less common and was due to fear of the anesthetist and fear of the baby's safety.

Conclusion: Preoperative anxiety was found to be important after elective cesarean section. The most important cause of mild anxiety was waiting for the operation (84.5%), followed by fear of medical errors (83.4%) and unexpected outcomes

INTRODUCTION

Anesthesia choice for cesarean delivery is an important clinical decision. When time and maternal condition permit, regional anesthesia most commonly spinal or epidural blockade – is the preferred option for elective cesareans. Regional techniques offer the mother the enduring advantage of being awake for the birth and avoiding risks related to endotracheal intubation and systemic anesthetic agents (Mostafayi, Imani et al. 2021). General anesthesia remains essential in emergencies and scenarios in which regional anesthesia is contraindicated.

Yet patient preference also plays a role. Fear of being awake during delivery, fear of pain with neuraxial techniques, or mistrust of regional blocks sometimes prompt patients or clinicians to choose general anesthesia. Recent studies indicate that preoperative anxiety contributes to these choices, shifting preferences toward general anesthesia in settings where anxiety is high (Dibabu, Ketema et al. 2023, Abd, Nattouf et al. 2024).

Preoperative anxiety before cesarean section is common across diverse settings. High prevalence

rates among women scheduled for elective cesarean sections have been reported by thorough cross-sectional research. Particularly high rates, occasionally surpassing 60 to 70 percent for clinically significant anxiety scores, are reported in studies carried out in low- and middle-income nations (Fentie, Yetneberk et al. 2022). When perioperative distress-sensitive assessment instruments are employed in high-income environments, similar trends emerge.

Preoperative anxiety does more than cause emotional discomfort. It also leads to clear and measurable physical responses in the body. Prior to anesthesia, it raises baseline blood pressure and heart rate and activates the sympathetic nervous system. According to Mostafayi, Imani, et al. (2021), these reactions make managing intraoperative hemodynamics more difficult and may necessitate the use of pharmacologic therapies such as vasopressors or additional fluid administration following spinal anesthesia. (Mostafayi, Imani et al. 2021)..

There is also evidence linking higher preoperative anxiety to greater anesthetic requirements during induction and to increased intraoperative awareness of pain or discomfort in some patients. Postoperatively, anxious mothers often report higher pain scores and greater analgesic use, which can delay mobilization and prolong hospital stay. In the neonatal domain, observational work has found associations between elevated maternal anxiety and short-term neonatal indicators, such as lower immediate adaptation scores, although causal pathways remain complex and partially mediated by obstetric and anesthetic factors (Ferede, Bizuneh et al. 2022).

Most women undergoing a cesarean section showed mild anxiety, with around 66 percent (96

patients) falling in this range. About 30 percent (43 patients) experienced a moderate level of anxiety. Only a small group, about 4 percent (6 patients), reported severe anxiety according to the STAIS score.

Materials and methods

Data was collected from Allama Iqbal Teaching Hospital Dera Ghazi Khan for duration of 4 months using a non-probability convenience sampling method, selecting participants based on availability and willingness rather than random selection. Our Sample Size was 145. Eligible women scheduled for elective cesarean delivery were approached during the study period. Each potential participant was visited before surgery for informed consent and data collection. The goal of the study was described, and participants were acquainted with the protocols. Responses were assessed in accordance with the normal protocol, and the STAI was administered in a controlled environment. Based on their overall scores, participants were divided into three groups according to the severity of their anxiety: mild (20–37), moderate (38–44), and severe (45–80). Next, a standardized questionnaire was used to gather clinical and demographic data. This method made it possible to recruit willing patients who fit the requirements up until the desired sample size was attained. Women between the ages of 18 and 40 who consented to participate and had an elective cesarean delivery were included in the study. Patients with refusal, psychological illnesses or trauma, use of anxiolytic drugs, linguistic challenges, or cesarean delivery due to life-threatening complications for the mother or fetus were eliminated. SPSS software was used to enter and evaluate the collected data.

Results

Cesarean Section History, Anesthesia Type, and Indications

VARIABLE	CATEGORY	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Previous cesarean section	Yes	89	61.4
	No	56	38.7
Previous CS complication	Yes	34	23.4
	No	111	76.5
Type of anesthesia in current CS	General	14	9.7
	Regional	131	90.4
Type of anesthesia in last CS	General anesthesia	18	12.4
	Regional anesthesia	83	57.3
	No previous surgery	44	30.3
Reason for CS	Repeated CS	63	43.5
	Twin	8	5.6
	Placenta problem	14	9.7
	Non-dilation of cervix	1	0.7
	Fetal presentation	10	6.9
	Uterus abnormality	11	7.6
	Hypertensive disorders	3	2.1
	Maternal choice	36	23.5

Possible Causes of Preoperative Anxiety

Item	Mild (n, %)	Moderate (n, %)	Severe (n, %)
Feeling worried about death	115 (79.4)	22 (15.2)	8 (5.5)
Fear of unexplained origin	113 (77.9)	27 (18.6)	5 (3.5)
Worried about financial loss	55 (37.9)	77 (53.1)	13 (9)
Concern about family	76 (52.4)	59 (40.7)	10 (6.9)
Postoperative pain	35 (24.2)	103 (71.3)	7 (4.1)
Fear of blood transfusion	50 (34.5)	87 (60)	8 (5.5)
Fear of physical disability	88 (60.7)	50 (34.4)	7 (4.8)
Fear of Complications	53 (36.5)	82 (56.6)	10 (6.9)
Cosmetic issues	113 (78)	25 (17.2)	7 (4.8)
Medical mistakes	121 (83.4)	21 (14.5)	3 (2.1)
Unable to recover from anesthesia	95(65.5)	48(33.1)	2(1.4)
Awareness during anesthesia/CS	104 (71.7)	34 (23.5)	7 (4.8)
Fear of gynecologist/professionals	104 (71.8)	37 (25.5)	4 (2.8)
Fear of anesthetist	100 (69)	34(23.5)	11(7.6)
Negative hospital experiences	108(74.5)	31(21.4)	6(4.1)
Lack of recognition by staff	108(74.5)	31(21.4)	6(4.1)
Bad obstetric history	106 (73.1)	35(24.1)	4(2.8)
Unexpected operation results	117 (80.7)	24 (16.6)	4 (2.8)
Waiting for operation	122 (84.5)	20 (13.8)	3 (2.1)
Fear for life/safety of fetus	103 (70)	32 (22.1)	10 (6.9)

Prevalence Anxiety Levels in Cesarean Section Patients (STAS)

DISCUSSION

The study's findings demonstrate that preoperative anxiety before cesarean birth is widespread and influenced by a variety of factors, including social conditions, obstetric history, previous surgical experiences, and particular concerns regarding anesthesia and perioperative outcomes. Most participants were in the typical childbearing age range, largely lived in rural settings, had limited formal education, and were housewife features that together create a profile of patients who may have reduced access to health information and less familiarity with hospital procedures. Similar links between low education, socioeconomic constraints, and higher anxiety have been observed repeatedly in obstetric populations, and they underscore the influence of social determinants on how women perceive and react to operative childbirth (Fentie, Yetneberk et al. 2022, Ferede, Bizuneh et al. 2022, Dibabu, Ketema et al. 2023). Concerns specific to anesthesia were prominent and multifaceted: fears of awareness during the procedure, worries about not waking from anesthesia, and distrust or fear of the anesthetist were repeatedly reported. These anxiety subtypes matter because they point to an information gap that is correctable. Studies that have tested focused educational strategies informational videos about anesthesia, structured preoperative counseling, and brief familiarization sessions report reductions in perioperative anxiety and improvements in patient satisfaction (Kalliyath, Korula et al. 2019, Che, Gao et al. 2020, Miremberg, Yirmiya et al. 2022). The present data therefore highlight an actionable target: improving pre-anesthesia communication and providing clear, culturally appropriate explanations about what patients can expect during regional or general anesthesia could reduce a large share of the fears observed.

Pain-related fears and worries about blood transfusion and physical complications accounted for much of the moderate anxiety reported in this cohort. These themes reflect both objective concerns pain management and transfusion safety are legitimate clinical issues and culturally mediated beliefs about the body and medical

interventions. Prior research has documented similar focal points of anxiety in obstetric surgical populations and has shown that addressing pain expectations and explaining transfusion protocols can alleviate anxiety (Dibabu, Ketema et al. 2023, Dana, Parami et al. 2025). In short, when care teams proactively discuss analgesic plans, outline transfusion criteria, and explain likely postoperative recovery trajectories, patients gain information that reduces uncertainty and lowers distress.

Situational factors such as waiting times, prior negative hospital experiences, and perceptions of insufficient recognition or respect from staff also played an important role. These are service-quality issues rather than intrinsic patient vulnerabilities, and they are therefore amenable to system-level fixes. Evidence shows that small changes clear staff introductions, transparent scheduling information, and efforts to shorten or better manage waiting periods can improve patient comfort and trust, thereby diminishing preoperative anxiety (Maghalian, Mohammad-Alizadeh-Charandabi et al. 2024). This study's emphasis on waiting and negative institutional encounters suggests that improving the patient experience in the preoperative area could be as important as clinical counseling in reducing overall anxiety.

CONCLUSION

The level of preoperative anxiety in elective cesarean deliveries was observed to be elevated. Here is a clear, human-tone summary that highlights the main and highest-percentage causes: There was no significant cause of severe anxiety. The most common cause of mild anxiety was waiting for the operation, reported by 84.5 percent of the women, making it the biggest contributor. Fear of medical errors (83.4%) and unexpected outcomes of surgery (80.7%) were identified by a large number of patients as the primary causes of their anxiety. In addition, a large number of women expressed fear of dying (79.4%), fear of cosmetic changes (78%), and inexplicable fears (77.9%). Fear of the anesthetist and gynecologist, unpleasant experiences in the hospital, unfavorable past experiences in

obstetrics, and lack of support from hospital staff were some of the other fears expressed. Based on 71.3% of the patients, fear of postoperative pain was the most prevalent factor in moderate anxiety. Concerns about money (53.1%), complications (56.6%), and fear of blood transfusion (60%) were also expressed.

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